

Vitenskapskomiteen for mat og miljø
Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment

Declaration of consent (photo)

I hereby consent to the recording of photographs, and that this material may be used by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM) and the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC), on internal and external channels/platforms such as vkm.no and LinkedIn.

Name of person (first name and surname)

E-mail address

Consent

I hereby authorise the recording of photos from the CHANGE workshop June 18th-20th 2024, and that this material may be used by VKM on internal and external platforms such as vkm.no and LinkedIn.